

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF VOCATIONAL COMPETENCIES IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION STUDENTS THROUGH INFORMATION-DESIGN TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The study presents a methodology for forming professional competencies in vocational education students using information-design technologies, as well as an analysis of the results of pedagogical experiments and trial studies conducted. Conclusions and recommendations based on these findings are also provided.

Introduction (Relevance):

In the current era of globalization, the formation of an innovative educational environment aimed at developing competencies in learners is of paramount importance for preparing competent mid-level specialists in economic sectors and socio-technical fields within the vocational education system. In Uzbekistan, the development of science and the entire continuous education system, including vocational education, is considered one of the priority directions of ongoing national reforms [1].

In recent years, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a series of decrees and resolutions to further develop vocational education. Notably, the Presidential Decree No. PF-158 dated October 16, 2024, "On Measures to Further Improve the System for Training Qualified Personnel in Vocational Education and Implement International Educational Programs," envisages a comprehensive structural and substantive reform of the country's vocational education system.

These legal and programmatic documents emphasize the need to enhance the quality and effectiveness of personnel training in vocational education, implement international educational programs, and prepare competitive mid-level specialists with high-level skills and competencies aligned with domestic and international labor market demands.

Consequently, based on advanced foreign experience, it is crucial to develop modern teaching methodologies in vocational education aimed at improving students' mastery of knowledge, forming general and professional competencies, as well as creating software tools and multimedia educational content.

Analysis and Methodology:

The concepts of competence and competency have been studied as scientific and pedagogical notions, as well as in relation to their formation and development within the educational process, by various researchers and educators. Among these scholars are Aronov A.M., Bermus A.G., Daminov O.O., Zimnya I.A., Zeer E.F., Karimova N.N., Lebedev O.Ye., Lukash

O.A., Najmiddinova Y.R., Igognina T.B., Turmatov J.R., Umataliyeva K.T., Qo'ysinov O.A., Khutorskoy A.V., Choshanov M.A., and others, who have conducted scientific studies in this area.

From a pedagogical perspective, the concept of competence is defined as a measure of the alignment between the skills and experiences of individuals with a certain socio-professional status and the actual level of the tasks they perform and problems they solve. The formation and development of professional competencies in future specialists occur during the teaching of curriculum subjects to learners.

This study focuses on the vocational education direction of "Computer Graphics and Design Operator" and examines the methodology for forming and developing professional competencies in learners during the teaching of the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies" using information-design technologies. It also presents an analysis of the results of pedagogical experiments and trial studies conducted in this context.

In the education system, including vocational education, the formation of learners' general and professional competencies is informed by the scientific and methodological findings of scholars such as Arkhangelskiy S.I., Bepalko V.P., Zakirova F.M., Kagan M.S., Mamatov D.N., Muslimov N.A., Reznichenko M.G., Fayzieva M.R., among others. It also draws on the psychological-pedagogical works of researchers such as Vygotsky L.S. and Rubinshtein S.L. Based on these studies and our own research on forming professional competencies in vocational education through information-design technologies, an information-project technology model was developed. This model has demonstrated positive results in forming both general and professional competencies in learners within vocational education institutions.

Experiment:

To study the formation and development of professional competencies in learners within the vocational education direction of "Computer Graphics and Design Operator," the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies" was taught using information-design technologies. Pedagogical experiments and trial studies were conducted based on current educational standards, and their results were analyzed. The experimental work was carried out over the 2020–2023 academic years in three stages: exploratory research, theoretical-experimental stage, and trial-experiment stage.

To assess the level of formation of students' professional competencies, a criterion-based diagnostic method was applied, which included motivational, cognitive, activity-based, and evaluative-reflective indicators. Learners' professional competencies were evaluated according to a set of low, medium, and high criteria and indicators using information-project technologies. The experimental studies were conducted in vocational education institutions in Nukus City (Institution No. 1), Qamashi District (Institution No. 2), and O'rtachirchiq District (Institution No. 1).

This study presents the analysis of pedagogical trial experiments conducted at Institution No. 1 in Nukus City. A total of 45 students participated in the experimental (E) groups, while 44 students were in the control (C) groups. During the experiments, the level of formation of professional competencies in the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies," taught using information-design technologies, was determined according to

predefined criteria and levels. The effectiveness of the experiment was analyzed using mathematical-statistical methods, and appropriate conclusions were drawn.

The results of the mathematical-statistical analysis of the pedagogical trial experiments indicate that in the experimental (E) groups, the levels of formation of professional competencies were as follows:

- High level: 11.1% at the beginning of the experiment, increasing to 22.2% by the end.
- Medium level: 22.2% at the beginning, rising to 48.9% by the end.
- Low level: 66.7% at the beginning, decreasing to 28.9% by the end.

In the control (C) groups, the levels of formation of professional competencies were as follows:

- High level: 6.8% at the beginning, increasing to 13.6% by the end.
- Medium level: 18.2% at the beginning, rising to 25% by the end.
- Low level: 75% at the beginning, decreasing to 61.4% by the end.

These results demonstrate that the use of information-design technologies in teaching significantly contributed to the improvement of learners' professional competencies compared to the control group.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

Analysis of the results of the pedagogical trial experiments indicates that in the vocational education direction of "Computer Graphics and Design Operator," the level of formation of professional competencies in learners of the experimental groups, taught the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies" using information-design technologies, was 12% higher compared to learners in the control groups. This finding was confirmed using mathematical-statistical methods.

The proposed information-project technology expands and systematizes the previously applied project-based method. It enhances interdisciplinary connections, develops learners' skills for active independent learning, and significantly increases their creative engagement. As a result, the effectiveness of forming professional competencies in learners is substantially improved

References:

1. Mirziyoyev, Sh.M. Strategy of the New Uzbekistan. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2021, p. 465.
2. Ergashev, J.J. Theoretical Foundations for the Formation of General Competencies of Vocational Education Students. Journal of Public Education, ISSN 2181-7839, No. 2, 2022, pp. 10–12.
3. Ergashev, J.J. Information-Project Technology Model for the Formation of Students' General Competencies. Journal of Teachers and Lifelong Learning, ISSN 2181-7138, Karakalpakstan, No. 3/1-1, 2022, pp. 220–226.
4. Ergashev, J.J. Exhibition Modeling of the Educational Process Using Information-Design Technologies. Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art, Special Issue, 2023-03-31, ISSN 2181-4287, pp. 315–316.
5. Yusupov, A.I., Ergashev, J.J. Formation of Professional Competencies in Vocational School Students Using Information-Design Technologies. Bulletin of the National University of Uzbekistan, 2024, [1/11], ISSN 2181-7324, pp. 253–255.